

Ashoka's Dhamma: A Practical Approach of Life

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Abstract

This paper attempts to explain the main theme of Ashoka's Dhamma in a great detail. Ashoka was a patron of Buddha's doctrine and was responsible for raising Buddhism from the status of a local sectarian creed of eastern India to that of one of the principal religions of the world¹. As a prince Ashoka was known for his ruthless character. When he heard that his father was dying, he hurried to the capital and eliminated all his rivals to the throne. He had ambitious plans to expand his empire through military conquests. In his invasion of the neighboring state of Kalinga, many thousands were killed, wounded or captured. The tremendous loss of lives in this invasion proved a turning point in the life of Ashoka, who became a thoroughly changed man shortly after the Kalinga War, which took place eight years after his coronation; i.e., in his ninth Regnal year.

This paper also studies the circumstances by which Ashoka recommended compassion, reverence, sympathy and truthfulness and condemned cruelty, irreverence, intolerance and falsehood. He provided amenities for animals just as for men and repeatedly advised people to be kind to them and issued orders prohibiting the slaughter of numerous species of birds and beasts including aquatic animals. In Rock Edict III, Ashoka directs his officers, viz. Yuktas, Rajukas and Pradesikas, to go forth once every five years for preaching the message of Dhamma. In Rock Edict V, The Dhamma-Mahamattas and their offices were created in regnal year 13 to preach Dhamma as a part of their duty.

This paper narrates in detail about the third Buddhist Council, which was held at Pataliputra during the reign of Emperor Ashoka, the renowned Buddhist Monarch of the 3rd

century. At this council, the last section was added to the PALI Scriptures, the Kathavatthu of the Abhidhamma Pitaka, dealing with psychology and metaphysics². The conversion of Emperor Ashoka to Buddhism led to lavish royal patronage of Buddhist monks and monasteries. This inevitably led to many non-Buddhists joining the order not because they were genuinely interested in Buddhism, but because it enjoyed royal patronage.

This paper examines Ashoka's virtues to constitute his Dhamma. The following are some of the virtues strongly recommended by Ashoka on various occasions: -obedience to parents, high personages, elders and the aged; liberality to friends, acquaintances and relatives as well as to the Brahmanas and Sramanas. His declared policy, which was fully in accord with the Dhamma he preached, was to see to the welfare and happiness not only of his subjects, but also of the peoples of other lands beyond the borders of his empire, as if all men were his children. In this matter, he did not make many differences among men and animals³.

This paper signifies Ashoka's zeal in the propagation of Buddhism throughout the other neighbouring countries. About the year 246 BC. Emperor Ashoka sent his son Mahindra as the head of a mission to Sri Lanka. There he converted the king to Buddhism. The king supported these Buddhist missionaries and provided facilities for them in his capital. From there, they were able to carry on their work of spreading the teaching of the Buddha. According to the Sri Lankan tradition (Dipavamsa XI) the Sri Lankan ruler at that time should have been Mutasiva, whose son Devanampiya Tissa succeeded him in Ashoka's Regnal year 17. The title of Devanampiya prefixed to Tissa's name already suggests the influence of the style of Mauryan royalty⁴. Later Ashoka dispatched certain relics of the Buddha and then a branch of 'Bodhi tree' escorted by his daughter Sanghamitta, a nun. Buddhism had by now secured firm patronage from royalty, which henceforth it rarely lost until colonial times⁵. As a whole, it is justified that Ashoka had a practical approach of life.

Introduction

Emperor Ashoka was a versatile genius and one of the most remarkable personalities in the history of the world. He was at the same time a great conqueror and builder, statesman and administrator, religious and social reformer and philosopher and saint. He was the third king of the Mauryan dynasty, who was widely known for his 'Dhamma'.

As a matter of fact, 'Dhamma' is the Prakrit form of the Sanskrit word '*Dharma*', virtually untranslatable into English owing to its use in a peculiarly Indian context. It has been variously translated as morality, pity, righteousness and so forth. It was in the conception of this policy regarded in the background of Mauryan India, that the true achievement of Ashoka lay. Previously, Ashoka's 'Dhamma' has been interpreted as a synonym for Buddhism. But actually Ashoka's Dhamma was a policy rather of social responsibility than merely of demanding that the entire population should favour Buddhism. It was the building up of an attitude of mind in which social behavior, the behavior of one person towards another, was considered of great importance. It was a plea for the recognition of the dignity of men and for a humanistic spirit in the activities of society.¹

Dharma or Dhamma, means to a Hindu 'the rule of life for each man as determined by his caste and station or in other words, the whole duty, religious, moral and social of a man born to occupy a certain position in the world.'² For many ages past this conception of 'Dharma' has been inseparably associated with the notions of caste. Each caste has its own dharma, and conduct most proper for the member of one caste is responsible in the highest degree for a member of another. In Asoka's time, caste although in some respects less rigid than it has been since the shock of the Muhammeden invasions, which did so much to solidify the institution, was well developed and the new current Hindu notion of 'Dharma' does not seem to diverge widely from that entertained by the followers of the Brahmanical law.³

It has been suggested that the ‘Dharma of Ashoka’ is in fact original Buddhism, as preached by the Buddha, and what we know today as Buddhism are theological encrustations added through the course of centuries.⁴ Unfortunately, there is not enough cross evidence to prove the validity of this view. An intensive analysis of the chronological sequence of Buddhist literature has yet to be undertaken, and even the results of such an analysis may leave us uncertain of the sequence. On the basis of the work that has been done so far, it is thought that Ashoka was familiar with much that is now found in the Nikayas,⁵ and that a major portion of the Nikayas existed in the 4th century B.C.

I am of the opinion that the Dhamma was Asoka’s own invention. It may have been borrowed from Buddhist and Hindu thought, but it was in essence an attempt on the part of the king to suggest a way of life which was both practical and convenient, as well as being highly moral. If we look at the Ashokan edicts, we find that Asoka did not regard himself as the great elect in his relations with his subjects, but rather as a father-figure. He constantly stresses the father-child relationship between the king and the populace. “.....savve munise pajã mamã; athã pajãye ichhãmi hakam kimti savvena hitasukhena hidalokikapãlalokikena yũjjevũ ti tathã..... munissesu pi ichhãmihakam.....”⁶ (*All men are my children, and just as I desire for my children that they should obtain welfare and happiness, both in this world and the next, so do I desire (the same) for all men*).

Really, this type of paternal attitude is a new feature in the relationship between the king and the population. It is the practical approach of Ashoka that made him the greatest emperor of the world. The 2nd Rock Edict relates certain measures of social welfare which are included in the working of Dharma.⁷ Medical centers for men and animals, the construction of roads supplied with well and lined with shady trees and the planting of medicinal herbs are amongst these measures. It is worth noticing that Asoka realized the importance of good communications.

The 3rd Rock Edict contains a vague reference to religion, in that it declares that liberality to Brahmans and Sramanas is a virtue.⁸ This type of statement shows his practical approach towards life and his qualities of a tolerant and broad-minded man of the time. If we have a glimpse over his 4th Rock Edict, we find that the 4th rock Edict was an important document in the development of Dhamma. The Edict says, “.... Ta ajja devãnampriyassa priyadassino rãnno dhammacaranena

bherighoso aho dhammaghoso Vimānadasanā ca hastidassanā ca aggikhamdhāni ca annāni ca divyāni rupāni dassayitpā janam...” (*But today, thanks to the practice of Dhamma on the part of the beloved of the Gods, Piyadassi the King, the sound of the drum has become the sound of Dhamma, showing the people displays of heavenly chariots, elephants, balls of fire, and other divine forms....*)

We are of the opinion that the view of Bhandarkar is closest to the idea that Asoka may have had when he composed the phrase. He writes, “The sound of a drum invariably precedes battle, a public announcement, or the exhibition of a scene to the people. But since Asoka entered on his career of righteousness it has ceased to be a summons to fight but invites people to come and witness certain spectacles; and as those spectacles are of such a character as to generate and develop righteousness, the drum has become the proclaimer of righteousness.” Really, the representations were shown during the few festival meetings of which Ashoka approved.

In the 10th Rock Edict, Ashoka denounces fame and glory and reasserts that the only glory he desires is that his subjects should follow the principles of Dhamma.¹⁰ He maintains that the reason for his efforts in this direction is twofold; obtaining merit in the next world, and the elimination of danger to men in this. Thus, the main theme of the edicts of Ashoka is what he calls ‘Dhamma’. In Minor Rock Edict III, the word is used in the sense of Buddha’s doctrine. But elsewhere it indicates a code of morals preached by Asoka probably following what he believed to be the teachings of the Buddha.¹¹

Emperor Asoka spread the Buddhist ideals, such as Ahimsa, Compassion, equality, respect for elders, discipline, welfare, simplicity, fragility and so on constitute the basis of humanism. Thus, the humanist approach of Buddhism and practical approach of life enshrined in the inscriptions of Emperor Ashoka has spread Buddhism in India and abroad. These are as follows:

Compassion and Major Rock Edict- XIII:

The conversion of King Asoka to Buddhism is truly in line with the respect and regard for humanism out of compassion. The Major Rock Edict- XIII declares as, ¹²

“When he had been consecrated eight years, the Beloved of Gods, the King Piyadassi, conquered Kalinga. A hundred and fifty thousand people were deported, a hundred thousand were killed and many times the number perished. Afterwards, now that Kalinga was annexed, the Beloved of Gods, very earnestly practices, Dhamma, desired Dhamma, and taught dhamma.”

Further, the compassion has been relised in the pillar Edict IV which states as, ¹³ “Men who are imprisoned and sentenced to death are to be given three days respite....”

Ahimsa and Major Rock Edict-I:

The Ahimsa, i.e., non-killing has been practiced by king Ashoka as the Major Rock Edict-I informs that the beloved of Gods, Piyadassi, the king has had this inscription on Dhamma engraved. Here, no living thing having been killed, is to be sacrificed; nor is the holding of a festival permitted because of the killings and sacrifices of animals in festivals.¹⁴

Respect for Elders and Kandharã Inscription:

The inscription in Greek and Aramaic informs that the obedience to mother and father, and elders and conformity with the obligations implied in this, is now in practice. ¹⁵Thus, it is the significance of practical approach of life, in which the practice of Dhamma is of value to all men and it will continue to be so.

Discipline and Schism Edict:

The Schism Edict ¹⁶ found at Sanchi, Sarnath and Kausambi talks about discipline by exhorting the Buddhist Sangha whoever creates a Schism in the order, whether monk or nun, is to be dressed in white garments, and to be put in place not inhabited by monks and nuns.

Welfare, Simplicity, Frugality and Major Rock Edict-III:

Emperor Ashoka imbibed the virtues of humanism and ordered his Yuktas (Sub-ordinate officers), Rajkus (Rural administrators), and Pradesikas (Heads of the Districts) to go on tour every five years in order to instruct people in the Dhamma. The inscription further says that it is good not only to spend little, but to own the minimum of property.

Thus, the humanist approach of Buddhism, which may be referred to 'the Dhamma of Ashoka', has helped propagate Buddhism in India and abroad. Ashoka understood a number of virtues to constitute his Dhamma. These included the least amount of sin and the greatest amount of good done to others as well as compassion, liberality, truthfulness, purity, gentleness and goodness, good conduct, self-control, purity of thought, gratitude and firm devotion are extolled as also the absence of violence, cruelty, anger, vanity and jealousy.¹⁷

Emperor Ashoka recommended compassion, reverence, sympathy and truthfulness and condemned cruelty, irreverence, intolerance and falsehood. The virtue on which he laid the greatest emphasis is regard for the sanctity of life. The other two virtues almost equally emphasized are liberality and reverence to all persons deserving of it by reason of rank, age or station. He provided for amenities for animals just as for men and repeatedly advised people to be kind to them and issued orders prohibiting the slaughter of numerous species of birds and beasts including aquatic animals for the preparation of curries for his own household and even banned festive gatherings in which meat was consumed by the people slaughter of an injury to animals were also generally prohibited on a number of specific days. The days specified were the three 'chauramasis' (the full moon days of the months of Ashadha, Kartik, and Phalguna) and the Tishya or Tisya Full Moon (in the month of Pausha), in each case together with the day immediately preceding and the following the full-moon, as well as the Buddhist fast days, i.e, the Eighth, Fourteenth and Fifteenth of each fortnight of a month.¹⁸

In the 6th Pillar verdict, Asoka briefly explains the purpose of the edicts in general.¹⁹ The primary reason was a concern for the welfare and happiness of his subjects, who, if they ordered their lives according to the principles of Dhamma

would attain happiness. He claims that in this effort of bringing Dhamma to his people, he has been impartial to all classes and all sects; and this, because he considers visiting the people personally to be his duty.

Thus, 'Ashoka's Dhamma' combined a system of welfare with his humanitarian approach. He genuinely wished Dhamma to be the means of communication between him and his subjects. The activities of the 'Dhamma-Mahamattas' are not restricted to any one group in the community. The 'Dhamma-mahamattas' are expected to work impartially amongst the various sects.

The 'Dhamma of Ashoka' emerges as a way of life incorporating a number of ideals and practices. Abstinance from killing was an important principle, as also was the insistence of considerate family relationships and social relationships, whether these were between parents and children, elders and young people, friends or various ideological sects. What would be regarded as a programme of social welfare, in 21st century parlance, such as providing medical facilities, good communications and prohibiting useless expenditure on superstitions, was included. Moderation was the key-note of thought and action, this is why, in interpreting the term 'Dhamma' we must beware of equating it with the Buddhist Dhamma or any other accepted system which was called by this generic term. Thus, the true interpretation of Dhamma can only come about after a detailed analysis of who used the term and in what context. Rock Edict XII speaks of his impartial consideration for all sects and his advice to the people of different religious sects and his advice to the people of different religious sects and communities to respect one another's creeds. He was definitely against extolling one's own sect and disparaging other sects and recommended restraint of speech in this respect.

Emperor Ashoka advised all classes of people to live together harmoniously in all parts of his empire. He also declared that what he wanted was the growth of the essentials of their respective Dhammas among all men. Such broadness of humanist approach is indeed remarkable. In Asoka's opinion, people of all sects have the desire for self control and purity of thought in common.

In pillar Edict VI, he refers to his eagerness to honour people of all sects. He felt that the honouring of other communities would lead to the glorification and

promotion of 'Dharma' as well as of all religious sects. He did not differentiate between the Brahmans and Sramanas and his superintendents of religious affairs were occupied, according to Rock Edict V and Pillar Edict VIII, with the welfare and happiness of all sects and communities like the Sudras, Vaisyas, Brahmans and Kshyatriyas as well as the Sramans, Ajivikas and Nirgranthas (Jains).²⁰

Conclusion:

Thus, we can say with certainty that the concept of 'Ashoka's Dhamma' was based on his humanitarian approach of life. Emperor Asoka, with the propagation of his Dhamma, made an attempt to humanize it and show that in fact what mattered most was virtuous behavior. In the propagation of his 'Dhamma', Ashoka was attempting to reform the narrow attitude of religious teaching, to protect the weak against the strong, and to promote throughout the empire a consciousness of social behavior so broad in its scope, that no cultural group could object to it. The reign of Emperor Ashoka has become the quintessence of ideal governance in modern age all over the Globe. He was the propounder of "Praja Sukhi, Sukhi Rajyam; Prajnam Cha hiteahitam." Thus, it is understood that emperor Ashoka had the practical approach of life. This is why, he is called Ashoka, the Great.

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